

IT as a resource for university examination, risks and challenges involved

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the changes universities have been forced to make during the times of COVID-19. There are different risks, challenges and opportunities at different places in the IT chain. The focus of this paper is mainly on Cyber Risk and its challenges. As the most important point of the cyber incidents can be related to different parts and organizational factors, a risk analysis will be made. Thereafter, the IT Governance & Outsourcing focus on how the IT of the organization should be organized and outsourced to cope with the change. Lastly, the BPI part will have a focus on the different business processes, related to cybersecurity incidents in the educational sector.

Keywords

Integrity, GDPR, cybersecurity, processing, data breaches

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought different challenges for the Dutch higher education worldwide. Going online can be seen as one of the biggest shifts in education. The university closings have affected learning and examination as a whole. Different challenges can be seen, which are also clarified in this paper. Online platforms were used in many countries, so as well in the Netherlands This brought different challenges for as well the students as the teachers. (Schleicher, 2020). The question that rises from this related to this research paper, is how this impacts the education and examination, the quality of degrees, and in which way the degrees can be seen as valid and relevant. Since more digitalization means more data available online - ready to be hacked. Take for example Maastricht University. Hackers broke into the system of Maastricht University via ransomware and demanded 30 bitcoins after which they would release the data of Maastricht University (NOS, 2020). Also mentioned by NOS (2020) is that the university should close down for a month if the

institution did not pay. Therefore, data protection seems more than ever an important topic that should be widely discussed among educational institutions. Another consequence of the digitalization is that academic exams are taken online where there are risks of fraud. Fraud deteriorates the integrity of degrees as a consequence. As this risks and challenges are all related to education, this paper raises the question how IT Security, Governance and Integration can be a resource of dealing with the crisis and which risks and challenges can be seen. (Schleicher, 2020)

OBJECTIVE

This research is designed to get into deeper detail to the GDPR objective. As being GDPR proof is an important goal of the Tilburg University and a continuing process for the organization as well for the staff as the students. A lot of attention has been paid to questions from staff, for example by the Data Representatives of the Schools and Divisions and by the Data Protection Officer. The IT department is consistently facing challenges regarding GDPR. The general question that arises from this GDPR topic, is: What are the challenges and how do universities protect data of their students? Moreover: universities seem more prone to fraud in an online environment. As being fraudulent corresponds with the integrity and validation of exams and degrees, the question that arises in this research paper: 'How do universities prevent fraudulent behavior in combination of being as data protective and privacy responsible possible, in a way that the integrity of degrees will not be badly affected?'

APPROACH

This research collects data from experts and existing research with an emphasis on how universities should deal with the challenges related to an online learning and study environment. General thoughts can be found and will be related to papers written by experts and this gives a main focus on qualitative research. GDPR related topics can be found in the general terms of Tilburg University and will therefore be used for background material. Citations

of experts will also be part of the aimed approach. Interviews conducted with experts help to get a more specified insight on the topic of this paper. Objects to be interviewed will be the professors and teachers of the master Information Management, as they fit the image of educational employees.

Furthermore, collected academic papers and written articles, websites and journals will be an important source of the research. The topics related to cybersecurity, ITG and BPI help to formulate a general answer on the research question and will be used to go in depth about the digital transformation the educational and career sector have made, during the COVID-19 crisis.

Lastly, a reference to models and BPI Activity diagrams will be done by reviewing the models and comparing the pre COVID-19 crisis to the COVID-19 situation. Also, the ITG & Strategic Sourcing models will be used to determine the shift the examination of students has made in the education sector.

MAIN FOCUS & RESEARCH

The focus of this paper will be on the public universities in The Netherlands. The purpose of universities is to educate, enlighten and cultivate students for society and their own future. Additionally, universities publish research in order to improve society. These universities are acknowledged globally throughout all sectors, as the students of these universities are seen as “society’s brightest minds”. University is the highest level of education in The Netherlands and there are relatively high standards for students to get in. Universities most likely support every sector in a different way, for example the medical sector heavily depends on universities for new high-position staff like doctors and surgeons, on top of the fact that university hospitals are essential for the research and innovation in the medical sector. There are 14 universities in The Netherlands that are funded by the government, all of them offering a wide variety of studies and degrees (Unipage, 2020). The key players in this market are the big and accredited universities like the University of Amsterdam, Erasmus University, Eindhoven University of Technology and Tilburg University. The focus in this research paper will be on Tilburg University. However, this paper will include other universities if in need of additional data. Every university hosts a massive IT environment that is essential to successfully running the university, for example: IT is essential to manage schedules, examinations and student portals. Moreover, IT enhances academic performance and productivity through for instance online study material and online study guidance. In recent years, universities in The Netherlands have become more used to combining

offline with online education. Therefore, the IT environment and resources have also significantly developed over the recent years and were (for the biggest part) already present before the COVID-19 outbreak. However, before the pandemic, the university didn’t have to rely solely on online education. When the COVID-19 outbreak reached The Netherlands, the Universities all decided that classes and examinations were to be suspended and held online to limit the spread of the virus for the safety of the students. As for everyone in the world, this new way of living has lots of challenges and risks. Online education means that there is more data available online, which means the university and its students are more vulnerable to data breaches and the integrity of the degrees is at stake. Furthermore, examinations are held online which opens a lot of opportunities for students to commit fraud. Students can let other people make their exams or work together on exams. Being prone to these risks might damage the reputation and credibility of universities and educational institutions as a whole. The world is changing and the universities have to keep up. Keeping up with this rapidly changing environment, however, is very demanding and complicated as universities keep operating and have to adapt constantly.

ANALYSIS

CYBERSECURITY

Along with the surge in the use of digital technologies, there has also been a rise in fraud (De’ et al., 2020). Because organizations and users have become more reliant on digital resources, targets of fraud and scams are rising as well.

Blended, hybrid and distance learning are all related to each other. The risks that can be associated with this form of learning, can be summarized in different ways. Based on the Risk Based Security Network 7.8% of the data breaches were related to educational institutions. (Risk Based Security, 2020)7As this was in Q1 of 2020, the forecast of the year 2020 has not been made yet, but it is thought that it will incorporate a rise of breaches. The following quote (Drew, 2012) already recognized the potential number of targets when it comes to the increased use of mobile devices: “The proliferation of mobile devices connecting to business networks and the increased migration of critical data processing and storage to the cloud have expanded the number of potential targets for cyberattacks.” The educational research will get a more collaborative and remote focus, which will bring different cybersecurity and privacy issues.

Looking at the case of Maastricht University, the data breach was possible because of many reasons. In this case, cyber criminals used ransomware that locks the system and retrieves data until a ransom is paid to the hackers. The risks related to cybersecurity can be classified as high, medium and low and can be interpreted in different ways. As stated in the article of the NCS, cybercriminals mainly address universities because these institutions are key contributors to the economy, skill development, and innovation. Despite this article being about universities in the UK, it is clear that universities in the Netherlands have the same contribution to society (NCS, 2020). Due to this impact on the society, also the impact of Cyber attackers can be related to this.

This paper continues to elaborate more on the risks associated with universities' cybersecurity and are multiple risks that can be identified will be discussed. Each of these risks have different likelihoods of happening and levels of impact. Some of the risks include phishing and ransomware risk, risk of malware, hacking risks (for example, through single factor login/password). Looking at the largest possible risks related to the digital transformation, it is possible to create a risk analysis. *Table 1* on the next page represents an overview of all the risks associated with cybersecurity of universities, i.e. a risk analysis matrix. This matrix gives a concise overview of the likelihood and impact of the mentioned risks. The columns stating 'overall risk' can be interpreted as the risk appetite of universities. If this risk appetite goes above the threshold of 10, controlling mechanisms should be set in order to bring down the likelihood, the impact, or both the likelihood and impact of the related risks. Several types of controls will be introduced below the table on the next page. These controls measures are "implemented to prevent, or else to detect and correct a control risk, i.e. an event that might result in not meeting objectives" (J. Hulstijn, personal communication, September 14, 2020). There are three types of control measures that will be explained next. First, there are preventative control measures, for example, paying for a meal before it is delivered to a customer (J. Hulstijn, personal communication, September 14, 2020). Moreover, preventative control measures also include providing education to people working as processors of information about the value of information, training those people to protect the information, and raising awareness about the way social engineers operate (Korpela, 2015). Second, detective control measures could be set into place. This way, no risks will go unnoticed. An example of such a measure is verifying a payment against the invoice, purchase order and delivery (J. Hulstijn, personal communication, September 14, 2020). The education preventative control measure can,

however, also be seen as a detective measure as the educated people will notice irregularities sooner. Lastly, corrective measures can be taken in order to respond to detected risks. Corrective actions such as "patching a system, quarantining a virus, terminating a process, or rebooting a system" can be taken if there are any incidents (Walkowski, 2019). The risk analysis is done in Table 1. As R1 has a quite high likelihood and impact, the overall risk can be implied as quite high as well (Porcedda, 2017). When such a risk occurs, the impact for the university can be high. Looking at how to prevent the personal data breaches, it is important to train people within organizations. As personal data has become an important topic within organizations, the scope of the training needs to be how employees and students, in the case of universities, should deal with protecting the data. GDPR control training contributes to a better risk mitigation and decreases exposure of personal data. Moreover, there is a general raised awareness about the value of information. Looking at the Maastricht University's case, an amount of 220.000 euros was paid to the ransomware cyber criminals. The main impact in this case is the financial impact. If there is to be a comparison between the amount that should be spent to train employees and the amount that needs to be paid for ransomware attacks, then, by means of a well-educated guess, this paper concludes that the training related costs are less than the payment for cybercriminals. In this case, **preventative control measures** - like the GDPR training - bring down the impact as well as the likelihood of personal data exposure.

The second risk (R2) from the risk matrix above has a relatively medium likelihood of occurring, but the impact is relatively low. Multiplying the likelihood with the overall risk, and risk appetite is calculated. The exposure of research data, however, can be seen as less harmful because it has no direct impact on the lives of researchers. The risk rises when the research data is not yet publicly available. In reaction to this risk, encryption of personal data is important for research data (Porcedda, 2017). This is mainly important because when the data breach happens, personal data will not leak together with the research data. As encryption of research data happens during the research and not after the research has taken place, this control measure cannot be of corrective nature. Also, it is not a detective measure as the control measure tries to prevent a risk from happening rather than detecting. Hence, encrypting the research data is also a **preventive control measure**.

R3 does not have a high likelihood of occurring, but the impact is high. By installing a safety guarantee, the likelihood and impact of this happening can be

lowered. In such a safety guarantee, virus detection software is also included. This way, computers and systems of the university are safer from any sort of virus infection. Therefore, the probability that computers and other IT systems of universities will be infected are reduced. Introducing a safety guarantee into the IT of universities will also help to safeguard the information on computers and systems from any kind of virus. Since the data is more secure with the safety guarantee, the impact of such a virus is reduced a little. To sum up, the proposed controls are **preventative** and **detective** types of controls.

The fourth risk that this paper treats is related to online credit card theft and other online financial data theft. Although its likelihood is medium, the impact of this risk occurring is very big. Theft of any kind of financial data, including credit card theft, has a significant impact on people. DelVecchio et al. (2002) explored how consumers, i.e. students, professors and other people at universities, assess the associated risks with the use of online credit cards. The results of that study show that people treat these risks in a multi-dimensional manner. For example, participants of that study were concerned about losing resources such as money and time if the risk occurred. In order to counter these risks, password and online safety training will be given to those concerned. This will reduce the likelihood of theft of financial data as people will be more conscious about these risks. Besides, the impact will also be reduced as more people think about the possible impact of such risks. This raised awareness will help people to realize that important information should be kept confidential and to themselves in a safe way. These types of controls are **preventative** as this paper aims to prevent any kind of online data theft.

The fifth risk, R5, concerns fraud of degrees and grading. This risk contains a relatively high probability and an even higher impact. The overall risk is the highest relative to the other risks. The reason for this is the compromised integrity of degrees and its accompanied grading. As this paper mentioned before, exams that are taken online are much more prone to be taken in a fraudulent way than with offline exams. But because of the CoViD-19 pandemic, universities are forced to provide online solutions for taking exams. Therefore, the opportunity exists for students to commit fraud and affect the integrity of university degrees in a negative way. Widianingsih (2013) mentioned that incentive, opportunity and rationalization are the three elements in the fraud triangle. As the opportunities to commit fraud increase, it is likely that more fraud will be committed. Fraud detection software could be the possible solution for this problem. With this kind of software, fraud during online exams will be detected. However, the power

of programmers and their knowledge about coding and hacking must not be underestimated since the IT world is evolving quickly. Implementing such software will decrease the likelihood of students committing fraud by means of building a safe, online reputation for students and their degrees. Introducing this kind of software is an example of a **detective** control mechanism.

Resilience

As being resilient is a way of dealing with cybersecurity threats, Weil & Murugesan (2020) highlight a way of dealing with this COVID-19 crisis. The NIST Cybersecurity framework (CSF) highlights a way of Identifying, protecting, detecting, responding and recovering. Mainly the recovering function can be applicable for cyber threats of universities. As being impacted by a cybersecurity incident, the recover function is an important fact for being resilient as university and organization.

Several solutions and mitigation perspectives can be implied in order to reduce the occurrence of cyber risks.

According to AON(2020), there are different ways of being Cyber resilient in COVID-19 times. Three key areas of focus can be explained:

- Defend against the Phishing Wave. This one emphasizes that the Phishing attacks are increasing and the attacks are increasing in the future.
- Test System Preparedness: This emphasizes the importance of constant testing because everyone is working from home.
- Brace for Disruption: Acknowledge that preventive measures could only go so far, as being prepared for them.

Looking at examinations, the cloud services, internet providers and service systems have to deal with a high demand and scaling of IT systems. The main focus on resilience should have been on the endurance and scaling of IT systems during the COVID-19 crisis, where demand peaked in a prominent way. This increasing demand brings also the challenge of being resilient. Mainly the above actions need to be kept in mind to stay resilient for the COVID-19 crisis.

Many vulnerabilities are affecting the remote workforce, as being a bigger target for hackers and intruders. This is caused by the fact that the way of working has been different since the past months. As BYOD, third party vendors and home office networks became more important in the educational system as well. (Well & Murugesan, 2020).

Risk	Risk ID	Likelihood	Impact	Overall risk	Control	Control ID	Likelihood	Impact	Overall risk (after control)
Exposure of personal data	R1	3	4	12	GDPR control training	C1	2	3	6
Exposure of research data	R2	3	3	9	Encryption of data	C2	2	2	4
Infection of university pc's and systems	R3	2	4	8	Safety guarantee	C3	1	4	4
Credit card theft and other financial data theft	R4	3	4	12	Password and safety training	C4	2	3	6
Fraud of degrees and grading	R5	3	4	12	Fraud detection software	C5	1	5	5

Table 1: Risk analysis of different cyber and IT threats

Solutions and mitigation

Taken all those risks and controls together, the example of Maastricht University is an example that can be applicable to each university. Looking at data risks, infection risks, credit card risks and fraud risks, these can be seen as a general implication for universities. The best way of controlling is keeping in mind how to keep your employees and students informed about what can happen during crisis times, how they should use their systems and what they should do if a data breach will happen. Risk management and identification is a process that needs to be done all the time, but in a more prominent way during crisis times.

In this way, universities and other research centers can take steps to remain proactive and mitigate their risks. It is important to understand the risks, practice good security hygiene and focus on employee engagement and monitor and evolve their Business Continuity and future needs.

The main point of university cyber risk management is thus the way of understanding the risks and know how to mitigate them. Keeping in mind that this can happen to each employee or student, it is important that systems help to avoid the occurrence of data breaches and cyber threats. With the controls and the safety measures, it is the best way to determine and reduce the likelihood of occurrence.

The main focus of decreasing the possibility of occurrence of data breaches, it is important that the risks firstly need to be identified and given a scale, as we did for universities. With this likelihood and occurrence, the way of dealing with them can reduce it. This means that employees and students also need to be aware of the possibility of occurrence from cyber risks. A constant security procedure and a way of mitigating security risks is the first thing universities should think about. Next to this, other fraudulent behavior from students also need to be kept in mind. This means that the educational institutions actually are dealing with two certain IT related topics in the way of Cyber and Risk Management. On the one hand, it is possible that universities are dealing with phishing, and exposure of personal data and on the other hand they are dealing with the way students try to be fraudulent and try to avoid the system of proctoring exams.

So an IT risk can not only be seen from outside the university, but also from inside the university. Fraudulent behavior, theft of data, and infection of systems are all factors that can be related to the cyber threats are in general thus more likely to happen and more important to mitigate in COVID-19 times, because the way of hybrid education and examination creates extra possibilities of

occurrence. Not only the IT experts are responsible for these risks, but the whole organization is responsible for dealing with the cyber threats and data breaches. Maastricht university is an example of how data breaches can happen, an important step in dealing with this is thus to show which risks are there and how they can be controlled and mitigated.

The process change and the differentiation of role performance during COVID-19 times, because of hybrid working will be explained further in the paper.

BUSINESS PROCESS INTERPRETATION

The COVID-19 situation has brought another phase for universities. As next to the new roles, the shift to online education has also made place for online examination. Even as in organizations, the universities also have different actors related to setting up programs and examinations. As the original examination process is a process of making, printing, testing and correcting, there has been a shift of the testing and correcting phase. (Weng et al, 2016) Because this phase is done by an online system, the Business Process has to be changed in a way of adding new actors and creating new processes, related to the activity diagrams.

Along with the surge in the use of digital technologies, there has also been a rise in fraud (De et al, 2020). Because organizations and users are relying on digital resources, targets of fraud and scams are rising as well. This causes the need for a fraud detection software integrated in the examination software.

Due to regulations, the 1,5 meter distance has made it impossible for students to go to campus and get their education and examination in that way. This caused a home staying situation and a computer based educational system. Next to the physical communication and discussion possibilities, also the examination has made a shift.

As the process of universities has changed, the process of examination has also made a shift. Looking at the different actors involved in this process, there has become an extra actor, to facilitate the examination. As seen in the Business Process Diagram visually given here under, there can be seen a shift in the way of working within universities. The shift from physical to online examination has created a need for online applications and systems. The online system meant here, is the Proctorio system, which has taken over the examination of exams. Proctorio has become an online examiner, but also a fraud and integrity system application for students. This means that it not only examines the knowledge, but also detects frauds and irregularities from students, while they are doing their exams. Where the university employees were firstly the actors, Proctorio can be seen as a replacement for these actors.

The shift in the system of educational systems can be seen in the examination way of working. This process has drastically changed. As this examination process has changed, it also causes a change in the graduation of a student, on which the focus also lies on. This graduation and receipt of diplomas, related to the online educational system, is a process that can be seen as one of the biggest changes in the systems since years.

The original login system did not change that much, as Osiris and Canvas were actors involved for a long time already. But where the original examination happened mostly on campus, a new actor is involved in the process, namely Proctorio. This is a new actor as being the new examiner. Next that the student fills in his exam in this application, also the fraud detection and grading system is implemented in this system. Next to the role that Proctorio has got, also the student feels another examination system as being a different actor than before. However in this main process of applying for exams and courses, and studying there is still the same process expected from students.

Pre COVID (Figure 1)

The pre COVID-19 situation shows a business process in which Proctorio is not added and not shown as a swimlane. This means that this is a general examination way.

Post COVID (Figure 2)

The post COVID-19 diagram shows an extra swimlane with Proctorio included, this means that the way of examination has changed.

Altogether, the two diagrams show how the way of examination has changed over time. Because of hybrid working

Figure 1: Pre COVID-19 Activity Diagram of examination on Dutch universities

Figure 2: Post COVID-19 Activity Diagram of examination on Dutch universities

IT GOVERNANCE & STRATEGIC SOURCING

This last part of the analysis elaborates on of CoViD-19’s total effect on IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing. First of all, the IT Governance part will be treated. After that, this paper explains the effect of CoViD-19 on Strategic Sourcing of universities.

IT Governance
 As previously indicated, IT has been getting more interwoven into society throughout the last decades. The CoViD-19 pandemic has made it more than clear that IT needs governance and structure. And so, along with that development, there has been a certain need for IT structure as well. A more general perspective on this matter is also known as IT Governance (ITG). Bianchi et al. (2017) mentioned that ITG calls for defining and implementing “formal mechanisms at the highest level in the organization taking into account structures, processes and relational mechanisms for the creation of business value from IT investments.” Bianchi et al. (2017) based their research on previous research done in the field of ITG for the financial industry (De Haes and Van Grembergen, 2009) and healthcare industry (Pereira et al, 2014b). The authors of the quote presented their findings in the form of baseline mechanisms for ITG in universities. As a matter of fact, two different universities from the Netherlands had participated in this research and therefore, the results of this research are to be taken into account with regard to the ITG solution for Tilburg University. The table below shows the proposed mechanisms that are aimed at providing a stable ITG context for universities.

Hence, introducing these baseline mechanisms will help to structure the IT of universities to be able to conduct business in a professional and proper way. Another important part regarding the IT governance of universities concerns the decision rights and the framework of accountability to promote a desirable IT behavior (Weill & Ross, 2004). The visualization of that framework is the IT Governance Arrangement Matrix next. As this thesis elaborates on the effect of CoViD-19, this thesis provides a pre-CoViD-19 IT governance framework as well as a post-CoViD-19 IT governance framework. Therefore, the first matrix is related to the IT governance before the pandemic and the second matrix relates to the adjustments made in order to continue business as usual

As universities are known to be centrally organized, it is straightforward to assume that the input of decision is based on the federal archetypes as this is the most common type. Also, the input is not very relevant to our research and therefore, an assumption was made. The black marked boxes indicate which archetype has which decision rights with regard to universities before the pandemic. It can be seen that the decisions about how IT is used in business processes (IT Principles) are taken by the archetype Business Monarchy (senior business executives). These business senior executives also have the decision rights for IT Architecture, IT Infrastructure Strategies, and IT Investments. However, since the rapid digitalization paved the way for more IT to be used in business processes in general, IT has thus become much more important. Now, the decision rights are more distributed among the archetypes. Next, these changes will be explained further.

Baseline mechanisms for Higher Education		
Structure	Processes	Relational
IT strategy committee	Strategic Information Systems Planning	Office of CIO or ITG
IT organization structure	Project governance/management methodologies	Knowledge management (ITG)
Business/IT relationship managers	Frameworks ITG	
IT steering committee		
ITG function/officer		

Table 2. Proposed baseline mechanisms (Bianchi et al., 2017).

PRE-COVID-19 IT GOVERNANCE ARRANGEMENT MATRIX					
Decision →	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure Strategies	Business Application Needs	IT Investments
Archetypes					
Business Monarchy					
IT Monarchy					
Feudal					
Federal					
Duopoly					
Anarchy					

Table 3. Pre-CoViD-19 IT Governance Arrangement Matrix.

POST-COVID-19 IT GOVERNANCE ARRANGEMENT MATRIX					
Decision → Archetypes	IT Principles	IT Architecture	IT Infrastructure Strategies	Business Application Needs	IT Investments
Business Monarchy					
IT Monarchy					
Feudal					
Federal					
IT Duopoly					
Anarchy					

Table 4. Post-CoViD-19 IT Governance Arrangement Matrix.

In the era of post-CoViD-19, IT Principles and Business Application Needs are now decided upon by the IT Duopoly (IT representatives combined with business representatives) since they are better at explaining the role of IT and respectively the needs in terms of business applications for companies. The IT Monarchy now is responsible for the IT Architecture and IT Infrastructure Strategies. This means that IT executives now design how IT will be structured and designed. From this matrix, it can also be seen that IT Investments decision rights remain distributed to the senior business executives. This way, they are still in charge of expenditures and investments.

STRATEGIC SOURCING

Tilburg University has already been outsourcing important services pre-CoViD-19, some examples are Canvas and Osiris. After CoViD-19 came up, issues arose concerning the integrity of the degrees. Tilburg University had to solve very fast as exams were still continuing, nevertheless there were no resources available in-house to solve this problem on the short term. There was no way for Tilburg University to counteract fraud in such a short period of time. However, there are several programs that counteract fraud through delivering a proctoring service. This program validates the identity of the student and ensures the integrity of the exam. The program scans for plagiarism, flags suspicious behavior and evaluates the room during the exam. Tilburg University chose Proctorio, one of the leading proctoring services used by over 400 universities. Proctorio was supposed to be the short term (and maybe long-term) solution to counteract fraud during exams and keep the integrity of degrees intact. Many students were against the implementation of Proctorio, students were worried that their privacy was being violated by the program and felt like they didn't have any say in the process. It was either complying and taking exams with Proctorio or don't take the exam and fail your courses and incur study delay. Moreover, Proctorio needs a stable internet connection, a webcam and a good computer to run flawless. If a student for some reason gets disconnected from the internet during the exam the student will fail the exam. Some students who don't have access to these resources have also voiced their dissatisfaction by claiming it is unfair to implement this program if not everybody can make use of it correctly. If this is the case and it is actually unfair to students without access to these resources, is the integrity of the exam still intact? Proctorio is still being used even though there are disadvantages and many complaints by students. It is still seen as a way to keep the integrity of the degrees intact during the CoViD-19 crisis.

DISCUSSION

Looking back at the introduction of this paper, we had two main objectives. Firstly, we considered the challenges that IT departments of Dutch public universities face in relation to the GDPR guidelines. Secondly, the IT transformation as a result of the CoViD-19 pandemic was taken into consideration. This transformation has resulted in a variety of challenges to protect the integrity of education as well as the prevention of fraudulent behavior. Both of these topics were approached from three different angles, the cybersecurity and risk management, Business Process Integration and IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing perspectives. While all of these sections yield interesting insights in the topic by themselves, this discussion will emphasize the value of taking all of these perspectives into account when navigating through this IT transformation.

Taking a look at the risk analysis that was performed in relation to the universities, the most impactful and most likely risk to take into consideration is the fraudulent behavior of students in relation to exams and degrees. As the university and IT environment have transformed into a mainly online environment, the risk of fraud has increased significantly. Not only does this issue play a prominent role in cybersecurity risk analysis, it requires the perspectives of Business Process Integration as well as IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing to work towards controlling the potential risks.

For the risk of fraudulent behavior in relation to degrees and exams, the risk analysis yields the suggestion to make use of fraud detection software. Before integrating such software into the university IT, it is essential that a thorough understanding of the requirements is established. Through strategic sourcing, the optimal solution should be found. While the current choice has resulted in the use of Proctorio fraud detection software at Tilburg university, it is recommended to continuously explore the options available as to deal with the current disadvantages that are faced. Comparison between different Dutch public universities can be of significant value to optimize the method of dealing with this issue. Subsequently, the Business Process Integration is of tremendous importance when dealing with rapid IT transformation. As seen in the figures, dealing with another external party increases the complexity of the examination network significantly. Taking into account the different perspectives on outsourcing fraud detection software, it is essential to continuously evaluate and develop the processes throughout the entire supply chain. Rapid change in the environment and a very volatile risk emphasize the importance of coordination when developing solutions.

Furthermore, not only the outsourcing of certain software raises the importance of coordination and development. The protection of data and

information in the IT system is a concern that every single stakeholder should be aware of as well. As data can be leaked, obtained or damaged through a wide variety of methods, it is important to take serious measures towards preventing this or dealing with it if it happens. The most obvious stakeholder in this process is the cybersecurity, where data should be protected well and

CONCLUSION

After looking at the impacts of COVID-19 on education it has been clear that there are many issues that need to be dealt with carefully. This paper aimed to identify the risks and challenges that arose from the forced transformation of the educational system due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Important risks and challenges have been identified while looking specifically at Tilburg University that require close monitoring and attention. Comparing the pre-COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 educational systems clearly showed that the education standard has gone from offline to online in a matter of weeks. Many things changed, for example, the roles of decision making have shifted from the business monarchy to the IT monarchy. Pre-CoViD-19, the business monarchy made the choices, even regarding IT. However, post-COVID-19 this had to change because everything related to IT and the wrong choices could have disastrous consequences for the university. The IT department had to have a say due to their expertise and experience and that is why the decision making roles shifted to the IT monarchy. Moreover, universities did not own the resources to fully support this transformation and this resulted in outsourcing of different tasks the university couldn't perform on its own. Additionally, the sudden transformation from offline to online resulted in three main issues arising concerning online education. First of all, online education means that way more personal data is available online, and thus also more vulnerable data online. A case has been discussed where this ended in a tragedy where Maastricht university was ordered to pay 200.000 euros to a group of hackers to get the data back of the students that were hacked. Furthermore, the integrity of the degrees is at stake as a result of online examinations. Online education means online examinations and this leaves a lot of room for students to commit fraud when they are taking an exam on their own laptop or computer or by letting other people make their exams. Fraudulent students do not deserve a degree but if not noticed will still get one, and this will hurt the integrity of the degree. To counter this, Tilburg and many other Dutch universities chose to implement a proctoring service that evaluates the room, flags suspicious behavior and checks for plagiarism. However, the

implementation of Proctorio, the proctoring service, did not come without its issues. Students and many third parties complained about a privacy violation because the program uses the webcam to look at the students and their surroundings. Despite these complaints Tilburg University has chosen to keep Proctorio to ensure the integrity of the degrees. In order to find solutions to these problems, time has to pass to be really able to see the consequences. Students have to get used to online education and its complexities. In conclusion, Tilburg University has been able to transition from offline to online education in a short period of time. However, there are still issues that need to be addressed and closely monitored in order to minimize the impact of these issues in the future.

REFERENCES

- AON. (2020). *Risk Alerts - Maintaining Cyber Resilience in the COVID-19 World*. Retrieved October 5, 2020, from <https://www.aon.com/apac/insights/risk-alerts/2020/maintaining-cyber-resilience-in-the-covid-19-world.jsp>

- Bianchi, I., Sousa, R., Pereira, R., & Hillegersberg, J. (2017). Baseline mechanisms for IT governance at universities. In *Proceedings of the 25th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS)* (pp. 1551-1567).
- De', R., Pandey, N., & Pal, A. (2020). Impact of digital surge during Covid-19 pandemic: A viewpoint on research and practice. *International Journal of Information Management*, June, 102171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102171>
- Li, Z. X. (2015). The Development and Design of Online Examination System Based on ASP.NET. *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, 727-728(Eeais 2016), 930-933. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/am.727-728.930>
- Risk Based Security. (2020). 2020 Q1 Report Data Breach QuickView. *2020 Q1 Report Data Breach QuickView*. <https://pages.riskbasedsecurity.com/en/2020-q1-data-breach-quickview-report>
- Schleicher, A. (2020). *the Impact of Covid-19 on Education Insights From Education At a Glance 2020*. 1-31.
- NCS 2020, the Cyber threat to universities, assessing cyber threat to UK universities <https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/report/the-cyber-threat-to-universities> [Accessed 28th of September 2020]
- NOS. 2020. Hackers Universiteit Maastricht Zaten Maanden In Netwerk; 200.000 Euro Betaald. [online] Available at: <https://nos.nl/artikel/2321732-hackers-universiteit-maastricht-zaten-maanden-in-netwerk-200-000-euro-betaald.html>> [Accessed 10 September 2020].
- Pereira, R., da Silva, M. M., & Lapão, L. V. (2014). Business/IT alignment through IT governance patterns in Portuguese healthcare. *International Journal of IT/Business Alignment and Governance (IJITBAG)*, 5(1), 1-1
- Porcedda, M. G. (2017). Big data breaches? Harms of datafication to privacy rights. *Paper for the TILEC - GovReg Workshop 'Economic Governance of Data Driven Markets,' August 2013*, 1-32.
- Risk Based Security. (2020). 2020 Q1 Report Data Breach QuickView. *2020 Q1 Report Data Breach QuickView*. <https://pages.riskbasedsecurity.com/en/2020-q1-data-breach-quickview-report>
- Schleicher, A. (2020). *the Impact of Covid-19 on Education Insights From Education At a Glance 2020*. 1-31
- Walkowski, D., 2019. *What Are Security Controls?*. [online] F5 Labs. Available at: <<https://www.f5.com/labs/articles/education/what-are-security-controls#:~:text=Corrective%20controls%20include%20any%20measures,process%2C%20or%20rebooting%20a%20system.>> [Accessed 9 October 2020].
- Weill, P., & Ross, J. W. (2004). *IT governance: How top performers manage IT decision rights for superior results*. Harvard Business Press.
- Weil, T., & Murugesan, S. (2020). IT Risk and Resilience-Cybersecurity Response to COVID-19. *IT Professional*, 22(3), 4-10.
- Widianingsih, L. P. (2013). Students cheating behaviors: The influence of fraud triangle. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 2(2), 252.
- Weng, G., Zheng, X., & Zhang, Y. (2016). The Analysis and Design of Online Examination System Based on B/S. *Advances in Engineering Research, Volume 17* 642-67
- Unipage. (2020). Universities in the Netherlands | List of Dutch colleges and institutes / Rankings. Unipage.net. Retrieved 1 October 2020, from https://www.unipage.net/en/universities_netherlands.

